

Shelf Life and Vitamin Composition of Black Plum (*Vitex doniana*)

Bread Spread for Adults in Enugu, Nigeria

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Abstract: The study determined Shelf Life and Vitamin Composition of Black Plum (*Vitex doniana*) Bread Spread Stored at Ambient Conditions in Enugu, Nigeria. The study adopted an experimental design. The study was conducted in Enugu State. The study population comprises of bread spread samples produced and stored for experimental analysis, which were subjected to laboratory determination of shelf life and vitamin composition. Data were analysed using mean and standard deviation. Findings of the study indicated that the shelf life determinants included protein, moisture and the Viable Counts. From the analysis, protein content decreased over the weeks; from 6.6 at the start to 6.1 at 3 weeks; 5.4 at 4 weeks, among others. The total viable count (TVC) cfu/g of the produced black plum spread slightly decreased, increased and later decreased over the weeks. Findings reveal that vitamin analysis was conducted using atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) and flame photometry to quantify the levels of Vitamins A, B₆, B₁₂ and E in the final product. The results indicated that the vitamin compositions of the black plum spread had Vit A: -0.35 mg for BPS, Vit B₆: -BPS contain 0.04 mg. The findings suggest that black plum spread not only offers extended shelf life with appropriate storage but also serves as a rich source of essential vitamins beneficial to human health

Keywords: Adults, Black plum, Shelf Life, Vitamin composition.

1. Introduction

Bread spreads are food products designed to complement bread by improving taste, texture, and nutritional contribution. They are commonly applied in thin layers and may be fruit-based, fat-based, or composite formulations derived from plant or animal sources. In Nigeria, bread consumption is widespread across socio-economic groups, making bread spreads an important vehicle for nutrient delivery. However, many conventional commercial spreads, including margarine, mayonnaise, and sugar-based jams, are characterized by high levels of saturated fats, refined sugars, and additives, which reduce their nutritional quality and raise health concerns when consumed frequently (Akubor, 2018; Porsgaard, Overgaard & Krogh, 2021). This situation has intensified interest in the development of healthier, plant-based bread spreads produced from locally available raw materials. Plant-based bread spreads are defined as spreads formulated entirely from plant-derived ingredients such as fruits, nuts, seeds, and natural sweeteners. They are increasingly valued for their contribution to dietary fibre, bioactive compounds, and essential vitamins, while being free from cholesterol and typically lower in saturated fats compared to animal-based alternatives (Reddy, 2019; Danielle & Shilpa, 2023). Marianne & Caroline, (2020); FAO, (2022), emphasizes the use of indigenous fruits in spread formulation as a strategy to improve nutritional quality, enhance food security, and promote sustainable utilization of local biodiversity which can be by Black plum.

Black plum (*Vitex doniana*) is an underutilized indigenous fruit widely distributed in Nigeria and other parts of sub-Saharan Africa. The fruit is traditionally consumed fresh or processed into beverages and is also recognized for its medicinal relevance in local diets. Scientifically, black plum has been reported to contain appreciable amounts of vitamin C, vitamin A, B-complex vitamins, and vitamin K, alongside minerals such as potassium, calcium, and iron (Poulose et al., 2018; Adepoju et al., 2021). In addition, the fruit is rich in dietary fibre and antioxidant compounds, including phenolics

and flavonoids, which contribute to oxidative stress reduction and improved metabolic health (Marianne & Walsh, 2020; Oboh et al., 2022). These nutritional attributes make black plum a promising raw material for functional food development, including fruit-based bread spreads. Despite its nutritional value, the application of black plum in standardized, value-added food products such as bread spreads remains limited. Most existing uses are informal, seasonal, and lack scientific evaluation regarding nutrient composition and storage stability. Converting black plum into a bread spread offers advantages such as improved shelf utilization, ease of consumption, and potential for household and small-scale commercial production. However, fruit-based spreads are particularly susceptible to quality deterioration due to microbial growth, enzymatic reactions, and vitamin degradation during storage, especially under ambient conditions common in Nigerian households (Barba et al., 2017; Ibrahim, Ibrahim & Esther, 2022).

Shelf life refers to the length of time a food product remains safe, nutritionally acceptable, and organoleptically stable under specified storage conditions. For fruit spreads, shelf life is strongly influenced by factors such as moisture content, acidity, storage temperature, and exposure to light and oxygen. Vitamins, especially vitamin C and some B-complex vitamins, are highly sensitive to heat and prolonged storage, leading to potential nutrient losses over time (Rickman, Barrett & Bruhn, 2020; Oyinloye et al., 2023). Despite the relevance of these factors, there is a clear paucity of empirical studies examining the shelf life and vitamin composition of black plum (*Vitex doniana*) bread spread, particularly when stored under ambient conditions. This research gap is especially significant in Enugu State, Nigeria, where ambient storage is the predominant practice due to limited access to refrigeration. The absence of scientific data on how storage duration affects vitamin stability and shelf life of black plum bread spread limits its wider adoption and commercialization. Therefore, this study focuses on

determining the shelf life and vitamin composition of black plum (*Vitex doniana*) bread spread stored at ambient conditions in Enugu, Nigeria. By addressing this gap, the study provides evidence-based information to support the development of nutritious, safe, and locally sourced bread spreads, while promoting the sustainable utilization of indigenous fruits in Nigeria. Page | 82

1.1. Statement of Problem

Optimal nutrition is essential for maintaining adult health, managing chronic conditions, and supporting age-related physiological changes. As a result, there is increasing demand for nutrient-dense, plant-based food products that are rich in essential vitamins, antioxidants, and dietary fibre, while being easy to consume and digest. However, many conventional bread spreads commonly consumed in Nigeria, such as butter, margarine, and mayonnaise, are high in saturated fats and cholesterol and provide limited micronutritional benefits. Although plant-based diets are gaining attention, available spreads largely target general consumer markets and are not specifically formulated to meet adult nutritional needs or to provide documented micronutrient benefits. In Nigeria, black plum (*Vitex doniana*) is an underutilised indigenous fruit known to be rich in vitamins and antioxidants. Despite its nutritional potential, *Vitex doniana* have largely focused on its traditional uses, phytochemical properties, or general nutritional composition of the fresh fruit. However, no known study in Nigeria has systematically evaluated the shelf life under ambient storage conditions or the vitamin composition of a black plum-based bread spread. This absence of data limits the utilisation, commercialization, and nutritional validation of black plum spreads for household and market use. The lack of information on the stability, vitamin retention, and storage safety of black plum bread spread represents a significant research gap in food science and nutrition in Nigeria. Without such data, the suitability of this indigenous fruit for developing shelf-stable, vitamin-rich plant-based spreads

cannot be adequately determined. Therefore, this study seeks to address this gap by investigating the shelf life and vitamin composition of black plum (*Vitex doniana*) bread spread stored under ambient conditions in Enugu, Nigeria, thereby providing scientific evidence to support its nutritional value, safety, and potential as a functional plant-based food product. Page | 83

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the shelf life and vitamin composition of plant-based bread spread (Black plum: *Vitex doniana*) for adults in Enugu state, Nigeria. Specifically, the study aims to:

- (a) Determine the shelf life of the produced black plum bread spread under controlled storage conditions.
- (b) Analyse the vitamin composition (Vitamins A, B6, B12, and E) of the black plum bread spread.

1.3. Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- (a) What is the shelf life of the produced black plum bread spread under controlled storage conditions?
- (b) What is the vitamin composition (Vitamins A, B6, B12, and E) of the black plum bread spread?

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

The study adopted an experimental research design, specifically a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD), within a research and development (R&D) framework. This experimental design was appropriate for systematically evaluating the effects of controlled variables on the shelf life and vitamin composition of the developed black plum (*Vitex doniana*) bread spread. Storage time was

treated as an independent experimental factor and manipulated at predetermined intervals of 0, 2, 4, 6, and 8 weeks. Each storage duration constituted a treatment level and was applied under two storage conditions (refrigerated and ambient). By blocking the samples based on storage conditions and randomly assigning treatments within each block, the design minimized extraneous variability and enabled a clear assessment of how increasing storage time influenced shelf life and vitamin stability of the product.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

No human participants were involved in this study. The research focused exclusively on the laboratory-based development, storage, and analysis of black plum (*Vitex doniana*) bread spread, including the assessment of shelf life and vitamin composition under ambient storage conditions. As such, participant recruitment, consent, direct human involvement was not applicable. Thus, in compliance with institutional research guidelines, ethical approval for this study was obtained from the institution of the principal investigator. The research was strictly laboratory-based and involved no human participants or animal subjects. All experimental procedures were conducted using food samples under controlled conditions, adhering to standard laboratory safety and ethical practices.

2.2. Area of the Study

The study was conducted in Enugu State, Nigeria, due to the availability of black plum (*Vitex doniana*) in the area and access to well-equipped laboratory facilities at the University of Nigeria for product development and analysis. Enugu State also has abundant underutilised indigenous plant resources, including black plum, which are suitable for food product research. The location therefore provided both the raw materials and the technical facilities required for evaluating the shelf life and vitamin composition of the developed bread spread

2.3. Population and Sample

The research was laboratory-based and focused on the development, storage, and analysis of black plum (*Vitex doniana*) bread spread under ambient conditions. The study population therefore comprised the bread spread samples produced and stored for experimental analysis, which were subjected to laboratory determination of shelf life and vitamin composition in accordance with standard food science procedures.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

Two sets of instruments were used for data collection. The laboratory Test template: Shelf life and Vitamin composition of the black plum spread products.

The product production process is the systematic task of generating new products, either by introducing changes to an existing product or creating a completely new and original one (Rouse, 2020). Therefore, the process of processing black plum spread includes: The process of processing black plum spread includes 3kg of black plum. The handpicked black plum was sorted, clean. The clean black plum was scraped, extracted and afterwards was packaged so as to keep it safe and protect it from moulds and also to sustain the shelf life. The black plum spread contained 3kg of black plum, 50g of dates and 25g of lemon juice. Only dates were purchased from local markets in Nsukka. Black plums (3kg) were processed by adapting the production method of Abu (2007). The processing was carried out by the laboratory technician and the researcher: thus;

1. Raw Material Measurement: Three kilograms (3 kg) of fresh black plum fruits were used as the main raw material. Additional ingredients included 50 g of dates and 25 g of lemon juice. The dates were purchased from local markets in Nsukka.

2. **Sorting and Washing:** The black plums were handpicked and carefully sorted to remove unripe, damaged, or spoiled fruits. The selected ripe fruits were then thoroughly washed with clean potable water to remove dirt and impurities.
3. **Preparation of Fruits:** The thin apocarp (outer skin) of the black plums was removed. This was followed by scraping the pulp from the stony endocarp using a clean, sharp knife.
4. **Cooking of Pulp:** The extracted pulp (3 kg) was transferred into a clean cooking pot and heated for a few minutes until a smooth consistency was achieved.
5. **Stirring:** The mixture was stirred continuously for 20 minutes using a wooden spoon to prevent burning and to ensure uniform cooking.
6. **Addition of Ingredients:** The blended dates (50 g) and lemon juice (25 g) were added to the cooked pulp and mixed thoroughly until a uniform spread was obtained.
7. **Cooling:** The prepared black plum spread was allowed to cool for a few seconds at room temperature.
8. **Packaging:** The cooled spread was packaged in clean, airtight containers to protect it from contamination, mould growth, and to enhance shelf life.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

The Data for the study were collected through the Laboratory Test template, shelf life and mineral composition of the products.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

Data were analysed using means, t-test was used to compare means between the pre and post treatment, mean, standard deviation, standard error of the mean (SEM). P-value (0.5) was indicative of significance and Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used to compare and contrast means.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Shelf-life protein, moisture content and total viable count for 8 weeks of the produced black plum (*Vitex doniana*) spread.

Weeks	Protein	Moisture	TVC (X 10 ³)
2	6.65	72.70	2.9
3	6.2	73.45	3.6
4	5.50	74.10	6.10
5	5.05	74.70	8.70
6	4.50	81.40	10.50
7	3.60	79.85	2.10
8	1.85	82.45	3.70

Key: Sample: Black plum spread

The results presented in Table 1 reveal notable changes in protein content, moisture content, and total viable count (TVC) of the produced black plum spread over the 8-week storage period under ambient conditions. Protein content showed a progressive decline from 6.65% at week 2 to 1.85% at week 8. This reduction in protein during storage may be attributed to protein denaturation and degradation caused by prolonged exposure to ambient temperature and increasing microbial activity. Similar reductions in protein content during storage of fruit-based spreads have been reported in (Ibrahim et al., 2022; Oyinloye, Adeyemi, & Adedayo, 2023), studies, which indicate that enzymatic reactions and microbial metabolism contribute significantly to nutrient breakdown over time. The observed trend suggests that extended ambient storage negatively affects the nutritional quality of black plum spread, particularly its protein stability.

Moisture content, on the other hand, increased gradually from 72.70% at week 2 to 82.45% at week 8, with slight fluctuations observed at weeks 6 and 7. The increase in moisture content may be due to hygroscopic properties of fruit-based spreads, which allow them to absorb moisture from the surrounding environment. The finding above supports the findings of Barba et al., (2017); Ibrahim, Ibrahim, & Esther, (2022), where they noted that high moisture levels are known to create favorable conditions for microbial growth and biochemical reactions that accelerate spoilage. The presence of bioactive compounds such as flavonoids and tannins in black plum has also been associated with water retention, which further explain Adepoju et al., (2021), findings that the moisture increase during storage. This trend underscores the importance of moisture control in extending the shelf life of fruit spreads stored under ambient conditions.

The total viable count (TVC) results indicate an initial gradual increase in microbial load from 2.9×10^3 cfu/g at week 2 to a peak of 10.50×10^3 cfu/g at week 6, followed by a sharp decline at week 7 and a slight increase at week 8. The initial rise in TVC aligns with (Rickman, Barrett, & Bruhn, 2020), who noted that increasing moisture content and nutrient availability support microbial proliferation. The subsequent decline observed at week 7 may be attributed to depletion of available nutrients, accumulation of inhibitory metabolites, or increased acidity of the spread, which can suppress microbial growth (Oboh et al., 2022). Similar Oyinloye et al., (2023), explained that microbial dynamics have been documented in fruit-based spreads stored at ambient temperature, where fluctuations in microbial counts occur due to changes in intrinsic product properties over time.

Table 2: Vitamin (Vitamin A, B₆, B₁₂ and E) of the black plum spread.

Sample	Vitamin A (mg)	Vitamin B ₆ (mg)	Vitamin B ₁₂ (ug)	Vitamin E (mg)	TVC (cfu/ml)
BPS	0.35	0.04	0.01	0.17	4.10

Key: Sample: Black plum spread

Table 2 presents the vitamin composition of the produced black plum spread, showing the presence of vitamins A, B6, B12, and E, albeit in relatively small quantities. Vitamin A (0.35 mg) and vitamin E (0.17 mg) were present in higher concentrations compared to vitamins B6 (0.04 mg) and B12 (0.01 µg). These findings are consistent with Poulouse et al., (2018); Oboh et al., (2022), reports that fruits, including black plum, are particularly rich in fat-soluble antioxidants such as vitamins A and E, which play key roles in immune function and protection against oxidative stress. The lower levels of B-complex vitamins observed may be linked to their water-soluble nature and susceptibility to degradation during processing and storage.

The recorded TVC of 4.10 cfu/ml in Table 2 indicates that the spread remained within acceptable microbiological limits at the time of vitamin analysis, suggesting that the product was still microbiologically safe at that stage. However, the combined effects of declining protein content, increasing moisture, and fluctuating microbial load highlight the limitations of ambient storage for prolonged periods. Overall, Rickman et al., (2020), findings demonstrate that while black plum spread retains valuable vitamins and exhibits moderate shelf stability, nutrient losses and microbial changes become more pronounced with extended storage. This underscores the need for improved preservation strategies or reduced storage duration to maintain both nutritional quality and safety of black plum (*Vitex doniana*) bread spread stored under ambient conditions

Implications and limitations

The findings of this study have important implications for adults, food and beverage workers, students and lecturers of Home Economics, curriculum planners, and food and beverage companies. The results provide useful information on the shelf life and vitamin stability of black plum (*Vitex*

doniana) bread spread stored under ambient conditions, which can support the utilization of locally available fruits in food product development, teaching, and small-scale food processing. The study also contributes to knowledge that may guide curriculum enrichment and promote innovation in indigenous, plant-based food products. Despite these contributions, the storage duration was relatively short, which may not fully capture long-term shelf life behavior of the product. Also, the sample size was small, as the study was limited to laboratory-produced samples, which may affect the generalizability of the findings. Lastly, the study tested a limited range of vitamins, and other micronutrients were not analyzed. Additional limitations included constraints related to laboratory analysis, time, and financial resources, which restricted the scope of the investigation.

Suggestions for further research

The following are the suggestion for further studies

1. Extending storage periods, increasing sample size, and analyzing a wider range of vitamins and nutrients,
2. Exploring other locally available plant-based spreads in different states or geopolitical zones.
3. Identification and quantification of specific microbial species present during the storage period. This will enhance understanding of spoilage organisms, potential pathogens, and their implications for food safety and shelf life (ICMSF, 2002).
4. Controlled experiments assessing the impact of different packaging materials and environmental conditions (e.g., humidity, temperature) on the physicochemical and microbiological quality of the black plum spread are recommended to clarify anomalies like the week 7 moisture drop.

5. Investigating the bioavailability of micronutrients in the spread and exploring fortification strategies (e.g., with vitamin B12 and E) could make the product more nutritionally beneficial, especially in contexts where it may be promoted as a functional or supplemental food item.

4. Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that bread spread can be processed from black plum fruit. The study determined black plum (*Vitex doniana*) spread's shelf life and Vitamin composition for Adults in Enugu, Nigeria. The study adopted experimental research design. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Findings of the study indicated that the shelf life determinants included protein, moisture content and total viable count measured over a period of 8 weeks. The spread was prepared under controlled laboratory conditions and stored at ambient temperature. Vitamin analysis was conducted using atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) and flame photometry to quantify the levels of Vitamins A, B₆, B₁₂ and E, in the final product. The product is still safe for consumption for a period of two months. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that Foods and Nutrition lecturers should acquire relevant skills required for entrepreneurship training Government and School management should provide relevant tools and equipment's as well as equipped food and nutrition laboratories for effective practical training. There is need for frequent food exhibitions, food funfair as this will enable the students to display some of the items produced by them for others to see and this type of exercise could also to encourage the students and organizing seminars and workshops for lecturers on ways of improving on what the already know is also very important.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Conceptualisation: B.I.A & N.M.E

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Funding Acquisition: B.I.A & N.M.E

Investigation: B.I.A & N.M.E

Methodology: B.I.A & N.M.E

Writing original draft, review and editing: B.I.A & N.M.E

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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